

IMPORTANCE OF BORROWED WORDS IN THE FIELD OF CULTURE AND ART

Davronova Asila

4th year student of the Faculty of Foreign Philology of Termiz State University

Ibragimova Gulshana

4th year student of the Faculty of Foreign Philology of Termiz State University

Abstract: Borrowed words are now available in a variety of fields. In particular, political, economic and others. In this article, we will consider the analysis and origin of some of the borrowed words found in the field of art.

Keywords: native word , culture , arts , borrowed , word meaning

INTRODUCTION

As to the origin English words may be classified into two large sets: native and borrowed words. A native word is a word which belongs to the original English word stock, as known from the earliest available manuscripts of the Old English period. A borrowed word or a borrowing is a word taken over from another language and assimilated in phonemic shape, spelling, paradigm or meaning, or at least in some of these aspects, according to the standards of the English language. The term borrowing belongs to diachronic description of the word stock thus the words 'wine, cheap, pound' were introduced by the Romans into all Germanic dialects long before the Angles and the Saxons migrated to the British Isles and nowadays they are not distinguishable from words of native origin.¹ Lexicology as a part of English language and science that studies words, aims to classify English words in various ways, however historically the English words can be considered anything but uniform. In general, the words consist of two groups - the native stock of words and the borrowed stock of words. In terms of numbers, the borrowed stock of words is considerably larger than the native stock of words and it comprises only 30 % of the total number of words in the English vocabulary, whereas the native words form the main part of the most frequent words, which are in fact used in speech and writing. Translation loans are words or expressions formed from the elements existing in the English language according to the patterns of the source language (the moment of truth - sp. el momento de la verdad). International words. There exist many words that were borrowed by several languages. Such words are mostly of Latin and Greek origin and convey notions which are significant in the field of communication in different countries. Here belong names of sciences (philosophy, physics, chemistry, linguistics), terms of art (music, theatre, drama, artist, comedy), political terms (politics, policy, progress). The English language became a source for international sports terms (football, hockey, cricket, rugby, tennis). Since English words are being used a lot in our language, naturally, everyone is interested in their etymological origin.

MAIN BODY

The development of cultural achievements of other ethnic groups, adapting them to their ethnic traditions and way of life, interests and aspirations promote interaction of different nations with a specific system of values and way of activity. In the course of evolution each culture addresses either to the past or to the experience of other cultures.

Borrowings in the process of cross-cultural interaction are an important factor of cultural and social change. The synthesis of cultural elements defines the essence of the world of culture

¹ <https://literature.academicjournal.io/index.php/literature/article/view/586>

in general. The evolution of social and cultural systems, as well as the mechanisms underlying the conversion, determine the nature of the development of world culture.

As early as in the XVIII century the German philosopher Johann Gottfried Herder drew attention to the fact that the phenomenon of human history is explained by the deep relationship between cultures. The example is the continuity of ancient Greek and Roman culture.

"Culture" as a concept is highly-valued. The most common term describes culture as "a system of values, life views, patterns of behavior, norms, a set of techniques and methods of human activity, objectified in subject, physical media (means of labor, signs) and transmitted to future generations". The interaction, in turn, reflects the universal type of connection between the subjects of certain relationships, involves the one-time existence of these entities and influence on each other. The concept of "intercultural cooperation" was introduced into scientific circulation by G. Treyger and E. Hall, defining it as an ideal goal to which man should aspire in his desire to adapt to the world around him in the best possible and effective manner.²

Adopted words are mainly used in situations where a word that exists in one language has no alternative in another language. In particular, in the field of art, there are borrowed words in several departments. We will consider some of them. Opera; Symphony; Oratorio; Estrada;³

Opera: OPERA (lat. opera - product of labor, work) is a musical dramatic art genre. Opera is a mixed (synthetic) genre that incorporates several art forms; in it, the forms of dramaturgy, music, visual art and dance art are connected in an integrated stage process. But music takes the leading place among them.

Symphony: Symphony (Ancient Greek: symphōnía - "harmony") is the leading genre of symphonic music, the highest form of instrumental music in the composer's direction. Designed for symphony orchestra performance;

Oratorio: Oratorio (lat. oratorium - chapel) is a large piece of music created for solo singers, choir and orchestra, usually based on a dramatic plot.

Estrada: Estrada (Spanish - taxasupa), pop art - 1) in a broad sense - general expression of entertainment, popular artistic (eternal, musical, dance, entertainment, etc.) genres and forms; 2) in the narrow sense - a type of professional stage art.

CONCLUSION

To sum up, nowadays we can come across catchphrases in every aspect of our life. We can encounter it not only in the field of art and culture, but also in many other fields such as commerce, trade, industry, and sports. As you know, this topic is very comprehensive. Therefore, it cannot be explained by one or two scientific works. Much more research and research can be conducted in this regard.

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3. <https://lex.uz/docs/-5849580>

² Y. G. Volkov, V. I. Dobrenkov Sociology: Textbook / Ed. by prof. Y. G. Volkov. - M.: Gardariki, 2003, pp. 512.

³ <https://lex.uz/docs/-5849580>